

Unequal Heat Exposure across Wales: A Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Socioeconomic Deprivation

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GISRUK 2026

Summary

This study examines spatial and temporal inequalities in outdoor heat exposure across Wales and their association with socioeconomic deprivation. Using MODIS-derived land surface temperature (2010–2023), the Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation and spatio-temporal weighted regression, the analysis explicitly identifies where and when deprivation–heat relationships diverge from national patterns. Results show consistently higher heat exposure in more deprived areas, strong spatial clustering, and pronounced spatial non-stationarity, highlighting place-specific heat inequalities missed by global models.

KEYWORDS: Heat exposure, Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation, Spatio-Temporal Weighted Regression, Land Surface Temperature

1. Background

Anthropogenic global warming has resulted in rising ambient temperatures and more frequent, intense, and prolonged heat exposure worldwide. Heat is now recognised as a major climate-related hazard with important implications for human health, and these risks are projected to intensify over coming decades (Ebi et al., 2021). Understanding the spatial distribution of heat exposure is therefore a key research priority.

Heat exposure is spatially heterogeneous, shaped by local climatic conditions (Perkins-Kirkpatrick & Lewis, 2020), land cover (Li et al., 2017), and the built environment. Urban–rural gradients, vegetation cover, surface materials, and settlement morphology generate fine-scale thermal variability that is not captured by regional or national averages (Hsu et al., 2021).

Socioeconomic deprivation is a key determinant of vulnerability to heat exposure. (Li et al., 2023). More deprived communities are often disproportionately exposed to elevated temperatures due to dense development, limited access to green space, and proximity to heat-retaining surfaces (Nishimura et al., 2025). Such unequal exposure can exacerbate existing social and health inequalities, reinforcing deprivation-related disparities in heat-related outcomes.

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Despite growing interest in deprivation-related heat inequalities, much of the existing literature relies on global or spatially stationary analytical approaches that assume uniform relationships between temperature and socioeconomic conditions across space and time (Osberghaus & Abeling, 2022). These assumptions risk obscuring localised and time-varying dynamics (Contreras et al., 2020). Capturing spatial and temporal heterogeneity in deprivation–heat relationships is therefore essential for identifying populations at greatest risk and informing targeted adaptation and public health interventions.

This study examines spatial and temporal variation in heat exposure across Lower-layer Super Output Areas (LSOAs) in Wales and its association with socioeconomic deprivation, explicitly modelling spatial and temporal non-stationarity using Spatio-Temporal Weighted Regression (STWR) to identify where and when deprivation–heat relationships diverge from national pattern (Fan et al., 2023; MITCHELL & CHAKRABORTY, 2014; Que et al., 2020a).

2. Methods

2.1. Datasets and Geography

The association between heat exposure and socioeconomic deprivation was examined using two primary datasets. Socioeconomic deprivation was characterised using the Welsh Index of Multiple Deprivation (WIMD) (Welsh Government, 2005) at the LSOA level and satellite-derived land surface temperature (LST). As WIMD is released periodically rather than annually, the most recent index available prior to each year of analysis was used, with missing years approximated using the mean of available scores to account for minor changes in LSOA boundary definitions. Outdoor heat exposure was derived from 1 km × 1 km MODIS LST data (2010–2023), with missing values imputed using Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) implemented in Python. Models incorporated meteorological and environmental predictors, including HadUK climate projections tasmax/tasmin (1 km), Copernicus European Regional ReAnalysis (CERRA) 2 m and skin temperature (~5.5 km), Spinning Enhanced Visible and InfraRed Imager (SEVIRI) LST (3 km), Landsat LST/NDVI (30 m resampled to 1 km), elevation, and seasonal terms. The study covered all 1,912 LSOAs in Wales.

2.2. Spatio-Temporal Modelling

STWR was employed to model spatial and temporal non-stationarity in the association between socioeconomic deprivation and heat exposure. STWR is a local regression approach that allows model coefficients to vary across both space and time, enabling identification of localised and time-varying relationships and detection of locations and periods where deprivation-related heat inequalities were most pronounced.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Figure 1 compares annual mean land surface temperature (LST) between the most deprived and least deprived LSOAs from 2010 to 2023. Across most years, LST was consistently higher in the most deprived areas, and the difference is larger during hotter years. While both deprivation groups follow similar temporal patterns, the persistent elevation of LST in more deprived LSOAs indicates a sustained disparity in heat exposure rather than an effect driven by isolated hot years.

Figure 1- Comparison of most deprived areas and least areas against heat exposure through the time

Figure 2 shows the 2018 distribution of weighted average land surface temperature (LST) for the two most deprived and the two least deprived deciles. The least deprived areas show a more concentrated distribution, while the most deprived LSOAs exhibit a broader spread with more observations at higher temperatures, indicating greater within-group variability and more frequent high LST values.

Figure 2- Comparing the two most deprived deciles and two least deprived deciles

3.2. Spatio-temporal geographically weighted regression

STWR was applied, with bandwidth and smoothing parameters optimised using a reproducible random subset of 400 LSOAs and then applied to the full dataset. While the global linear regression explained negligible variation, STWR achieved a substantially improved fit and markedly better information criteria, demonstrating that spatially and temporally varying relationships capture structure missed by global models (Table 1).

Table 1- Accuracy metrics and coefficients comparison

Metric	Global Regression	STWR (bandwidth = 40)
Residual sum of squares	9133.536	1450.744
Log-likelihood	-4208.006	-2449.085
AIC	8420.012	4966.883
R2	0.002	0.841
Deprivation coeff	0.085	0.562

Table 2- Summary of local statistical significance and direction of deprivation coefficients from the STWR model for the final study year (2023)

Quantity	Value
Total LSOAs (last-year surface)	1912
Critical $ t $ threshold	3.564
Significant ($ t > 3.564$)	1454 (76%)
Positive significant	1070 (56%)
Negative significant	384 (20%)
Non-significant	457 (24%)
Positive coefficients ($\beta > 0$)	1318 (68.9%)

Local parameter estimates revealed pronounced spatial heterogeneity in both the magnitude and direction of deprivation effects. Extreme coefficients were confined to a small number of locations while the central distribution remained stable, indicating that improved model performance reflects coherent local variation rather than overfitting. Deprivation was a statistically significant predictor of heat exposure across a substantial proportion of LSOAs (Table 2). Model optimisation favoured limited temporal smoothing, suggesting that dominant spatial non-stationarity with a secondary temporal component.

Figure 3- LSOAs with positive coefficient

Based on Figure 5, despite the absence of a global association, local modelling indicates that over 56% of sampled LSOAs exhibit a significant positive deprivation–heat relationship.

4. Future directions

This analysis used annually aggregated MODIS data; finer temporal resolution (e.g. monthly) may better capture temporal non-stationarity in deprivation–heat relationships. Future work will extend the framework to indoor heat exposure, providing additional insight into deprivation-related heat vulnerability.

5. Acknowledgements

This research was conducted as part of the Maternal And preGnancy hEalth aNd elevaTed heAt (MAGENTA) project, funded by the Wellcome Trust, an organisation approved by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI).

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Biographies

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